

Studies on the effect of different ligands and percent composition of organic solvents on solvent-solute interaction by interferometric technique

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Abstract : In the present study the solute-solvent interaction was investigated by ultrasonic velocity and density measurements at 0.1 M concentration of three solutes in dioxane-water mixtures of different percentage composition. The aim of the study was to find the effects of protic/aprotic nature, polarity/non-polarity, dielectric constant, hydrogen bonding of solvent with resonance stabilization, structure, different substituents and effect of hetero atoms on ligands in solvent-solute interactions from the acoustic parameters β_s , ϕ_v , ϕ_k , L_f , R_A and Z .

Keywords : Solute-solvent interactions, acoustic parameters, interferometry.

Ultrasonic measurements have been widely applied to explore informations regarding internal structure, molecular association, complex formation, internal pressure and stability of coordination complexes¹. It is also used extensively to study the molecular interactions in pure and binary liquids. Considering the importance of ultrasound in the determination of physical parameters it was thought interesting to determine the densities and ultrasonic velocities of 0.1 M solutions of three ligands, namely 2-amino-4-hydroxy-*s*-triazine (L_1), 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (L_2) and 1-(4-hydroxy-5-benzyl-6-methyl)pyrimidino-3-phenylthiocarbamide (L_3) in different percentage of dioxane-water mixture as a solvent. From these values adiabatic compressibility (β_s), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k), intermolecular free length (L_f), relative association (R_A) and specific acoustic impedance (Z) were calculated.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Double-distilled water was used during the study. Ultrasonic interferometer from Mittal Enterprises, model MX-3 with accuracy of $\pm 0.03\%$ and frequency 1 MHz was used for the measurement of ultrasonic velocities. Temperature variation was maintained within ± 0.1 °C. Densities were measured with the help of bicapillary pycnometer. Dioxane was distilled as described. The ligands were prepared by reported methods².

The adiabatic compressibility (β_s) and solvent (β_o) are given by :

$$\beta_o = \frac{1}{V_o^2 d_o} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_s = \frac{1}{V_s^2 d_s}$$

V_o , d_o , V_s , d_s stands for velocity and density of solvent and solution respectively.

Apparent molar volume has been calculated from the relation :

$$\phi V = \frac{1000 (d_o - d_s)}{C d_s d_o} + \frac{M}{d_s}$$

M = molecular weight of ligand and C = molarity of solution.

Apparent molar compressibility was obtained from the equation :

$$\phi K_{(s)} = \frac{1000 (\beta_s d_o - \beta_o d_s)}{C d_s d_o} + \frac{\beta_s M}{d_s}$$

Specific acoustic impedance (Z) and relative association (R_A) are functions of ultrasonic velocity and are computed from the equation :

$$Z = V_s \times d_s ; R_A = \frac{d_s}{d_o} \left(\frac{V_o}{V_s} \right)^2$$

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The sound velocities of ligand L_1 , L_2 and L_3 were measured at the same concentration of ligands (0.1 M) and the same dioxane-water mixtures.

Results and discussion

A study of β_s , ϕ_k , ϕ_v , L_f , R_A and Z and partial molar volume properties directly reflects the structural interaction of solvent with solute and provides informations regarding complex formation, stability, internal structure, molecular association and internal pressure. The values of acoustic parameters calculated are presented in Tables 1 to 3. It is observed from the Tables 1 to 3 that β_s values for L_1 are smaller than those for L_2 and L_3 . These values are found to be more or less continuously decreasing with increasing dioxane concentration in all systems. The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) for each system is found more or less to decrease. As the percentage of dioxane in dioxane-water system increases, protic nature, polarity,

dielectric constant and tendency of formation of hydrogen bonding in solvent in the system decrease. Hence it may cause decrease in β_s values for L_1 , L_2 and L_3 . The higher values of β_s for L_2 and L_3 than L_1 are due to difference in structure of ligands. L_1 contains symmetrical triazino nucleus having three carbon atoms and three nitrogen atoms in hexacyclic ring but L_2 and L_3 ligands contain pyrimidino nucleus having four carbons and two nitrogen atoms in hexacyclic ring. In L_3 ligand phenylthiocarbamidino is substituted on amino group which is substituent of pyrimidino nucleus, while this amino group is free in L_2 . It means in L_3 , amino group is blocked while in L_2 it is free hence β_s and ϕ_v of L_3 are smaller than L_2 . In the present study it was noted that the nature of ring structure, total number of different atoms present in the ring, resonance stabilization in the ring, total no. of electron lone pairs present on hetero atoms, electron donating and electron attracting substituents in the molecule (ligand) will directly interfere

Table 1. Acoustic parameters in different dioxane-water mixtures

System : Ligand AHT (L_1), temp. = 30 °C, concentration : 0.1 M, ultrasonic frequency = 1 MHz

% Dioxane	U_s (m s ⁻¹)	d_s (kg m ⁻³)	$\beta_s \times 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	ϕ_v (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\phi_k \times 10^{-10}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	L_f (Å)	R_A	$Z \times 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
70	1526.1	979.2	4.385	1.8369	-8.5067	0.01321	0.9446	1.4943
75	1525.9	982.4	4.372	1.7051	-5.3919	0.01319	0.9458	1.4990
80	1525.6	982.6	4.373	1.9847	-2.0394	0.01319	0.9432	1.4990
85	1525.2	991.2	4.337	1.2004	-1.0672	0.01314	0.9506	1.5117
90	1524.6	993.1	4.332	1.0868	-2.0708	0.01313	0.9518	1.5141
95	1524.1	995.8	4.323	0.8532	-1.1978	0.01312	0.9541	1.5177

Table 2. Acoustic parameters in different dioxane-water mixtures

System : Ligand AHMP (L_2), temp. = 30 °C, concentration : 0.1 M, ultrasonic frequency = 1 MHz

% Dioxane	U_s (m s ⁻¹)	d_s (kg m ⁻³)	$\beta_s \times 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	ϕ_v (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\phi_k \times 10^{-10}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	L_f (Å)	R_A	$Z \times 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
70	1489.8	1000.2	4.505	-0.2966	-5.8692	0.01339	0.9726	1.4901
75	1489.8	1000.8	4.502	-0.1554	-0.4842	0.01339	0.9713	1.4909
80	1489.9	1000.9	4.501	0.1349	2.6784	0.01339	0.9684	1.4912
85	1489.2	1003.8	4.492	-0.0544	8.9539	0.01337	0.9704	1.4948
90	1489.2	1004.3	4.490	-0.0245	8.8582	0.01337	0.9701	1.4955
95	1485.9	1005.3	4.505	-0.0838	26.0689	0.01339	0.9714	1.4937

Table 3. Acoustic parameters in different dioxane-water mixtures

System : Ligand AHMP (L_3), temp. = 30 °C, concentration : 0.1 M, ultrasonic frequency = 1 MHz

% Dioxane	U_s (m s ⁻¹)	d_s (kg m ⁻³)	$\beta_s \times 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	ϕ_v (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\phi_k \times 10^{-10}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	L_f (Å)	R_A	$Z \times 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
70	1497.3	1001.0	4.456	-0.28672	-10.7003	0.01392	0.9718	1.4987
75	1489.6	1001.9	4.498	-0.17544	-0.972116	0.01338	0.9724	1.4924
80	1489.6	1004.7	4.486	-0.15390	-0.127085	0.01336	0.9722	1.4966
85	1489.4	1006.1	4.480	-0.19300	7.15514	0.01336	0.9726	1.4985
90	1489.4	1006.3	4.479	-0.13318	7.32808	0.01335	0.9720	1.4988
95	1489.6	1006.5	4.478	-0.11321	23.1789	0.01335	0.9718	1.4992

Note

with the interaction between solute and solvent causing changes in β_s and ϕ_v values.

The continuous decrease in adiabatic compressibility (β_s) on increasing percentage of dioxane may also be interpreted in terms of electrostriction. At higher percentage of water some voids remain in structured water, thereby keeping solution compressible. But when the percentage of dioxane increases and of water decreases the voids become less making the solution less compressible. Thus electrostriction makes the solution less compressible.

It is observed that ϕ_k values increase continuously with the increase in percentage of dioxane for all the ligands. The positive values of ϕ_k for ligands indicate the electrostatic force in the vicinity of ions. It is observed that intermolecular free length (L_f) continuously decreases with increase in percentage of organic solvent for L_1 . For L_2 , L_f remains constant upto 80% then decreases and again increases. For L_3 it increases and then decreases. The increase of L_f value may be due to stronger interaction between ligands and solvent molecule at that particular percentage composition of dioxane-water mixture, while decrease in L_f values indicates weaker interactions. From these two observations it is clear that at a definite percentage composition of dioxane-water mixture

there is a stronger interaction between ligands and solvent molecules. Relative association R_A for L_1 and L_2 showed irregular trend with increase in percentage of dioxane-water mixture. This may be due to different electron withdrawing/releasing substituents present in the different ligands. The decrease in R_A values is due to the breaking of solvent structure. The specific acoustic impedance (Z) increases with increase in percentage of organic solvent for L_1 . For L_2 it increases continuously but decreases at 95% and for L_3 first it decreases upto 75% and then continuously increases with increase in percentage of organic solvent.

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